

The Preparation of Camphor from Pinene.

BY

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The preparation of camphor from French and American turpentine, the chief constituent of which is pinene, is already a commercial proposition. Nevertheless the details available in the scientific literature are meagre. We found that research was necessary before we could obtain a satisfactory yield of camphor from pinene. The results are published with a view to supplement the information available in the literature.

As our work was instigated by a desire to prepare camphor from Indian turpentine, which does not give any appreciable yield of pinene hydrochloride, we selected those methods which do not require the intermediate production of pinene hydrochloride. The process which has been worked successfully is as follows:—

Pinene \longrightarrow Bornyl salicylate \longrightarrow Borneol \longrightarrow Camphor.

Bornyl salicylate was prepared according to Chemische Fabrik von Heyden (D.R.P. 175097, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 92, *i*, 429). Two parts of salicylic acid and 1 part of pinene distilled from French turpentine were heated together for 17 hours at 110° and gradually raised to 150° in 11 hours. The product was shaken with aqueous sodium carbonate to remove unchanged salicylic acid,

extracted by ether; dried, freed from ether and distilled *in vacuo*. It gave 70.8 per cent. (reckoned on the weight of pinene) of bornyl salicylate distilling at 178—182°/7 mm. A large fraction distilled at 60—80°/7 mm., and could perhaps be utilised for the preparation of a further quantity of bornyl salicylate.

On using equal parts of salicylic acid and pinene (molecular proportions) the yield was 59 per cent. of bornyl salicylate.

Borneol was obtained by boiling 1 part of bornyl salicylate with 5 parts of 20 per cent. alcoholic potash under the reflux for 8—10 hours. The product was poured into water and steam distilled. The semi-solid which separated from the distillate was collected and pressed between blotting paper; the yield was 44 per cent. of the theoretical of fairly pure borneol. The oil which was removed from the solid during the filtration was re-saponified but did not give any appreciable yield of borneol. Saponification with aqueous and alcoholic potash under various conditions did not give any better yield.

Camphor was prepared from the borneol by shaking with 5 parts of 50 per cent. nitric acid (containing a trace of nitrous acid) for 3 hours in a shaking machine. The mixture was diluted with water and the camphor filtered off. Yield 50 per cent.

Attempts to obtain a better yield of camphor by directly oxidising bornyl salicylate, and attempts to use sodium peroxide as an oxidising agent, as described in the literature, were not successful.